

EU Fire Projects United

2nd Joint Newsletter

Challenges & Synergies

#EUFireProjectsUnited

What is EUFireProjectsUnited?

Firelogue is an EU Coordination and Support Action (CSA) which connects the three EU Innovation Actions (IAs / TREEADS - SILVANUS - FIRE RES) and supports them by integrating their results across all stakeholders and phases of Wildfire Risk Management (WFRM) and to connect them with existing insights from projects such as FirEURisk

Firelogue's main goal is to unite as many fire-related projects as possible and to identify fields for collaboration. So, Firelogue's first effort is to create common dissemination actions with the IAs and other fire related projects. #EUFireProjectsUnited consists of Firelogue, SILVANUS, TREEADS, FIRE-RES, FirEURisk, SAFERS, FIRE-ADAPT and PYROLIFE.

#EUFireProjectsUnited

A results map was developed by Firelogue to build a basis for the peer exchange across projects. The map will be integrated into the project website and should guide the development of cross-project publications. In addition, case study exchanges and peer learning as well as the development of a wildfire risk management data map are on the Firelogue agenda.

Finally, and in line with the development of policy recommendations, Firelogue will support the exchange about the coherence of different sectoral policies such as forestry, nature conservation, agriculture, mitigation, or bio-economy. Ideally, this will lead to the design of synergistic wildfire risk management approaches. However, this is a complex task that affects a large range of Green Deal projects. Coordination across the European Commission's Directorates is hence just as required as across the Green Deal projects and wider stakeholder community.

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Concrete Outcomes and Future Developments

A non-comprehensive overview of key achievements includes:

- The provision of new information and recommendations to capture the current state of the fuels across landscapes, offering insights for parametrizing management recommendations;
- The elaboration of recommendations for safe Wildland-Urban Interface architecture and resilient landscape design and planning;
- The exploration of options for enhancing public-private economic incentives and bioeconomy value chains as well as insurance solutions to effectively address EWE;
- The analysis of interoperability training needs between Member States;
- The setting of a basis for integrated advanced technologies for data acquisition
- The identification at the Living Labs level of specific challenges by the local Community of Wildfire Innovation;
- The engagement of stakeholders in fuel treatment prioritization, landscape planning, and risk awareness.

FIRE-RES future steps will especially revolve around the full deployment of all 34 Innovation Actions to be tested in the 11 Living Labs.

FIRE-RES

Challenges

The capacity to harmonise the results and innovations emerging in a variety of formats and sources will be crucial. Other particularly important points are the Open Innovation Challenge selected solutions, the FIRE-RES Innovation Actions and other project outcomes, as well as the Living Lab innovations and other sister projects' developments.

Synergies, Overlaps and Common Goals

In line with the WFRM Cluster Roadmap collaboratively developed with Firelogue, SILVANUS, TREEADS and FirEUrisk, FIRE-RES looks forward to strengthening the connection with the other EUFireProjectsUnited by contributing to the development of the joint WFRM Impact Assessment methodology. This will ensure that the knowledge and innovations produced are pooled to maximise outreach and incentivize constructive exchange and mutual learning.

[Find the latest item of news here](#)

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Concrete Outcomes and Future Developments

The diverse pilots have been implemented in different operational scenarios. In France, user products such as IoT sensors and social sensing fire detection systems were tested close to an industrial (potentially highly explosive) facility. In Australia, ground robots have been tested to map and survey the area. Future pilots, such as the one in Portugal, will focus on a case study that has a wildfire scenario impacting the electricity infrastructure. The goal is to test the platform in a variety of scenarios that will facilitate a highly adaptable approach to wildfire management.

Challenges

The ambitious scope of the project, which covers 12 pilots in 11 countries all over the world, at least 10 user products, and a large number of citizen engagement campaigns, provides certain logistical challenges. The feedback and the impact measurement of citizen and stakeholder engagement is of crucial importance. Finding the right balance between the beneficial aspects of fire and the dangers of extreme fire in the context of integrated fire management, considering the versatile use of technologies in the SILVANUS platform, is also a priority.

Citizen Engagement App tested in the French pilot

Synergies, Overlaps and Common Goals

The synergies and overlaps may be beneficial to all of the projects, as project outputs can potentially be shared and results can be therefore greater in the context of achieving the wildfire-related Green Deal goals. SILVANUS can use the outputs of other fire projects (e.g. the fuel map) to enhance the applicability of the platform.

SILVANUS Citizen Engagement Poster Exhibition in Rijeka, Croatia

A dissemination strategy with promotional videos, introductory webinars, newsletters, flyers and social media campaigns.

[Detailed results of SILVANUS available here](#)

Challenges

TREEADS is an ambitious project aiming to develop, optimize, and validate over 26 innovative technologies. One of the main challenges we faced in our second year was determining the specific requirements and operating procedures of these high Technology Readiness Level (TRL) solutions so that they could be seamlessly integrated into the TREEADS holistic wildfire management platform. To ensure a successful integration, our partners invested considerable effort in developing an integration plan and procedures.

Synergies, Overlaps and Common Goals

TREEADS collaborates closely with other EU fire management projects, addressing shared challenges and fostering synergies. To align with common goals, TREEADS actively engages in collaborative efforts, sharing communication materials, participating in joint initiatives, and contributing to the collective progress of IA members. This collaboration involves frequent synergy meetings, exchange of dissemination plans, and participation in shared events like workshops and conferences. Notable instances include the 1st Joint Dissemination Workshop on January 23, 2023, the Clustering event on November 22, 2023, and joint campaigns on fire-related international days. These synergistic actions enhance cooperation, promoting awareness, and collectively addressing significant challenges in the realm of fire management.

Concrete Outcomes and Future Developments

Among the future developments are the completion and review of the prediction models on future extreme wildfire regimes and continuing with the remaining pilot sides and demonstration areas exercises. Furthermore, upon the project completion it will be implemented the integration of the project results into existing systems (i.e. EFFIS), platforms and satellites services (i.e. Copernicus) and capitalization of results using knowledge Management platforms such as DRMKC/JRC including a repository of the fuel management tools and apps.

Challenges

Throughout the project the partners faced and overcame several challenges. Firstly, the use of consistent terminology definition and differentiation, which could create gaps in understanding and application. Additionally, the data collection for creating the fuel classification maps and the spatial resolution for each of the models depending on the available data and the analysis of those.

Synergies, Overlaps and Common Goals

FirEUrisk is actively collaborating with FIRELOGUE (is the precursor project) and the other Green Deal projects under the EUfireprojectunited initiative by participating in webinars and other clustering actions with the most recent project presentation to FIRELOGUE Clustering event. In these events the project is presented along with the up-to-date results and implementation of those if possible. FirEUrisk along with Firelogue co-organised the IX International Conference in Forest Fire Research in Coimbra with the participation of all the GD projects among others.

The FirEUrisk EUP (European Funded projects) Board has organized and participated in a number of webinars, events and conferences creating synergies and collaborations with European funded research (Respond-A, LIFE Resilient Forests, VESPRA, FireLINKS, PYROLIFE-ITN) and DG-Echo project, NEMAUSUS. The targeted projects have as main research topics climate change and WFRM and are sharing similar challenges and inspirations as FirEUrisk.

The webinars recording and other dissemination actions are listed in the FirEUrisk website and social media.

Concrete Outcomes and Future Developments

Training events delivered:

- 4 events focused on in-depth interdisciplinarity and intersectorality, and the integration of knowledge and skills.
- 4 workshops focused on dealing with knowns and unknowns.
- 5 events to disseminate knowledge to science and stakeholders, including:
 - An international symposium with 15 experts.
 - The PyroLife 2023 Conference.
 - 7 webinars
- 18 online audiovisual communication outputs.

Research publications:

- 15 research articles by ESRs in peer-reviewed journals

Resources

- 6 factsheets on ESRs' publications, summarizing the implications of the research for wildfire management and giving recommendations to emergency responders and policymakers.

PhDs completed

- 5 PhD thesis defended.

Career progression

- 6 ESRs on new positions.

Future developments

- Continue providing innovative and science-based solutions for managing (mega)fire risks in temperate and Mediterranean Europe.
- Continue enhancing career perspectives and employability of the ESRs still in the programme.
- Contribute to structuring doctoral research training at the European level and to strengthening the European innovation capacity.

Synergies, Overlaps and Common Goals

Potential synergies

- Knowledge exchange
- Sharing of wildfire-related events and results
- Sharing of job opportunities and potential candidates

Common goals

- Reduction of megafire risk
- Development of a “living with fire” approach

Concrete Outcomes and Future Developments

We are in the second year of the project; in June, we are gathering for the third time at the Brazil Study Hub. Future developments include the development of standardised protocols for quantifying the effects of IFM on carbon dynamics and the biodiversity of ecosystems, a review of fire-use terminology, and a book on IFM.

Synergies, Overlaps and Common Goals

Potential synergies

- Knowledge exchange
- Sharing of wildfire-related events and results

Common goals

- Role of IFM in tropical and subtropical ecosystem
- Study the impact of the use of fire on biodiversity and carbon dynamics
- Development of a “living with fire” approach

Concrete Outcomes and Future Developments

The main challenges of SAFERS are reaching end-users and engaging citizens. Overall, end-users have been reached throughout specific exploitation actions and during the field demonstrations. Indeed, during the French demo, several organisations from the Corsica region were involved in the fight against forest fires at different levels were invited to test the functionalities of SAFERS and provide feedback from the perspective of end-users. Personnel from the Fire and Rescue Service of Haute-Corse (SIS2B) also came to attend the demonstration.

A team of 14 firefighters from the SIS2B forest fire intervention group were engaged in the field exercise. In addition, external end-users were invited to participate in the demo, namely VOST (digital volunteers), Forest Defence Volunteers from Catalonia and the Croatian Rijeka Fire brigade. The field demonstration in Piedmont, El Perello and Greece Thessaloniki followed the same pattern where a wide range of end-users were involved such as Piedmont Civil Protection, AIB (Anti Incendi Boschivi), VV.F (Vigili del fuoco), Forest Defense Volunteers (ADF), Enervent S.L., HMOD, etc.

Concrete Outcomes and Future Developments

In the same vein, SAFERS project organized two webinars on November 6th and 8th 2023 with the support of Horizon Results Booster and in collaboration with other emergency management and wildfire risk projects, namely FIRELOGUE, OVERWATCH, and TREEADS, all funded by the EU. The first webinar, held on November 6th, focused on Activating Citizen Participation in Wildfire Risk Management. The second event took place online on November 8th to Showcase Innovations in Wildfire Risk Management while presenting results from EU-funded projects.

Both events aimed to demonstrate project strategies for engaging citizens in wildfire management while promoting technical and replication outcomes to various stakeholders, especially citizens, civil society, and NGOs. The participants presented in addition innovative technical results to stakeholders targeting primarily the potential end-users. Emphasis was also placed on enhancing collaboration and synergies among EU-funded projects. Both webinars were successful, bringing together interested participants (with 8 keynote speakers and more than 100 registrations) leading to constructive exchanges and synergies across the participating projects.

[LEARN MORE](#)

Synergies, Overlaps and Common Goals

SAFERS consortium has been active in creating synergies with other fire-related and European Earth Observation EU projects. For example, SAFERS took part of FIRELOGUE RIB meetings that gather several EU projects in order to enhance their research synergies and outcomes. The aim is to explore some collaboration actions, such as working on a common EU fuel map, collaborate on Fire risk management and producing a joint white joint paper about field demonstrations.

SAFERS has been additionally involved in the clustering event “Wildfire Risk Management Project (WRMP)” that gathered several EU projects and policy institutions in April 2022 to discuss the key priorities for cooperation. The project participated also in the “Fire Across Boundaries” conference and notably, the roundtable about "Future wildfire risk scenarios" addressing the expected impacts by the Green Deal related to building resilience into European landscapes" in October 2023.

SAFERS supported and participated in the workshop on “Wildfire Management Innovation and Policies” during the RISE-SD2023 event, organized by FIRELOGUE and FIREURISK with the support and participation from SAFERS, SILVANUS and TREEADS projects. Projects from the cluster EUfireprojectsunited are important allies for SAFERS given the common goal of developing an integrated fire management strategy to support societies becoming more resilient shared by initiatives like FIRE-RES and SILVANUS.

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End of Joint Newsletter

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